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1. Deliverable abstract

This deliverable report contains the updated DMP at the end of the first reporting period.

JUMP INTO SPACE Data Management Plan (DMP), agreed on by the partners, details how data are collected, processed, analysed, described, preserved, and shared throughout the project and after the project is completed. It outlines strategies for managing research data, ensuring compliance with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles, and adhering to EIC's Open Science requirements. This DMP ensures that JUMP INTO SPACE data is well-managed, accessible, and reusable, supporting scientific transparency and innovation in space-based solar energy research.

2. Data summary

2.1 Types and Formats of Data

The project will generate various data types, including:

- Experimental data from tandem PSC development and testing (txt, CSV, Excel, Origin)
- Simulation and modelling outputs (MATLAB, Python, COMSOL, Lumerical files)
- Images and microscopy data (TIFF, PNG, JPEG)
- Technical reports and publications (PDF, doc, ppt)
- Metadata (XML, RDF)

2.2 Data Origin

Data will be collected from laboratory experiments, computational simulations, and characterization studies performed by the consortium partners: UNITOV, HZB, ONERA, UNINOVA, SAULE, CEA, UNITO, and UNISI.

2.3 Data Volume

The estimated data volume is approximately 5-10 TB over the project duration, considering high-resolution images, simulation datasets, and experimental logs.

3. Data Storage and Backup

- Data will be stored in secure institutional repositories maintained by consortium members.
- Cloud storage solutions compliant with GDPR and EU data policies will be used.
- Regular backups will be performed on secure servers, with redundancy to prevent data loss.
- Access will be controlled, with authentication measures for consortium partners.

4. Data Access and Sharing

4.1 Access Policy

Public datasets will be shared via open-access repositories (e.g., Zenodo, OpenAIRE, EU Data Portal). Restricted access datasets will require consortium approval and may be shared under controlled agreements. Sensitive data (e.g. intellectual property-related data) will be protected through confidentiality agreements.

4.2 Open Access

Peer-reviewed publications will follow EIC's open-access mandate. Datasets underpinning publications will be deposited in open-access repositories (e.g. Zenodo, OpenAIRE, EU Data Portal) with DOIs assigned.

2.3 Interoperability

- Data will be described using standardized metadata formats (e.g., Dublin Core, DataCite).
- Use of open file formats (e.g., CSV, JSON) will be preferred where possible for ease of reuse.
- Compliance with discipline-specific standards for solar energy and materials science research will be sought.

5. Data preservation

- Data will be preserved for at least 5 years post-project completion in institutional and public repositories.
- Formats will be chosen to ensure long-term usability (e.g., non-proprietary formats like CSV, TXT, PDF).
- A sustainability plan will be developed to maintain access beyond the project's funding period.

6. Responsibilities and Resources

- UNITOV will oversee the overall data management process.
- Each partner will manage and curate their datasets before submission to central repositories.
- Data management training will be provided to consortium members to ensure compliance with the DMP.

7. Ethical and Legal Considerations

Compliance with GDPR and ethical guidelines for handling personal or sensitive data will be ensured. Personal data processing by the partners will be done in accordance with Article 15 of the Grant Agreement.

Intellectual property will be managed as per consortium agreements, ensuring proper attribution and licensing.

8. Updates

Following the withdrawal of SAULE from the project (officialized in September 2025), UNITOV, in agreement with the other partners, has proceeded with removing SAULE team members' emails from the project mailing list and has revoked them the access to the shared Teams folder and documents. Reports, presentations and other documents, prepared by SAULE from the kick off until the withdrawal, will remain in the project's shared drive.